

Another 1.0 g of the crude residue was also desalted by resin chromatography through Amberlite IRA 400 (OH) as before. The amino acids were eluted with 1 *N* acetic acid. The eluate was concentrated under reduced pressure and paper chromatographed in solvents I and II. Two amino acids found were identified as arginine and serine by co-pc with authentic samples.

All these amino acids from their mixture were isolated as individual ninhydrin complexes by preparative pc⁸ on Whatmann 3 mm using solvent-I as developing solvent and ninhydrin as spray reagent and heating the chromatogram at 100°. The colour bands were mapped out by pencil and *R_f* of each coloured band was compared with the *R_f* of authentic sample. Each band was cut out in small strips and the strips were moistened with 75% ethanol (10 ml) in petri dish for 0.5 h. The strips were then removed by thorough washing with 75% ethanol. The solution in the petri dish was transferred to a colorimeter tube and ninhydrin reagent (1 ml) (to ensure completion of reaction) added to it and warmed the mixture for 15 min. The coloured solution was cooled to room temperature, the volume was made up to 10 ml with 75% ethanol and optical density (O.D.) was measured colorimetrically⁹ at 540 nm by a VIS Bausch & Lomb Spectronic 20 spectrophotometer. The amount of each amino acid was obtained by interpolation of its O.D. in the standard O.D. vs concentration curve of authentic sample. The O.D. at different concentrations of the authentic sample were measured by adding 2 ml of reagent to 8 ml of solution in 75% alcohol and the resultant solution warmed on steam-bath for 15 min and finally the volume of the solution made up to 10 ml. For yellow coloured solution of hydroxyproline, O.D. was measured⁷ at 440 nm.

The relative occurrence of individual amino acids in μg per g of air-dried leaves, was found to be arginine, 98.0; tyrosine, 69.0; hydroxy proline, 32.9; valine, 16.0; serine, 16.0; glutamic acid, 15.3; methionine, 9.2; isoleucine, 7.8; aspartic acid, 6.7; leucine, 5.3 and glycine, 2.8. Among these, arginine, valine, methionine, leucine and isoleucine are essential amino acids.

Acknowledgement

Sincere thanks are due to Dr. L. M. Mukherjee of this Centre for providing facilities and to Dr. A. K. Chakraborty and Dr. M. M. Nandi of this Centre for authentic samples of amino acids, and to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. J. D. HOOKER, "Flora of British India", L. Reeve & Co., London, 1979, Vol. 2, p. 523.
2. "The Wealth of India, A Dictionary of Indian Raw Materials and Industrial Products", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1972, Vol. 6, p. 323.
3. M. MANZOOR-I-KHUDA, S. A. CHOWDHURY, T. REZA and A. K. CHOWDHURY, *J. Bangladesh Acad. Sci.*, 1981, 5, 55 and references therein.

4. B. DINDA and M. K. SAHA, *Phytochemistry*, communicated.
5. E. LEDERER and M. LEDERER, "Chromatography", Elsevier, New York, 1957, p. 127.
6. E. STAHL, "Thin-Layer Chromatography", 2nd. ed., Toppan, Tokyo, 1969, p. 737.
7. D. T. PLUMMER, "An Introduction to Practical Biochemistry", 2nd. ed., Tata McGraw-Hill, New Delhi, 1979, pp 83, 144.
8. D. ABBOTT and R. S. ANDREWS, "An Introduction to Chromatography", Houghton Mifflin Co., Boston, 1965, p. 18.
9. D. J. BHATT, A. J. BAXI and A. R. PARIKH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 98.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Microgram Amounts of Rhodium(III) with Methotrimeprazine †

B. KESHAVAN and P. NAGARAJA

Department of Post Graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, University of Mysore, Mysore-570 006

Manuscript received 14 January 1985, revised 24 June 1985, accepted 29 October 1985

IN continuation of our studies on *N*-alkylphenothiazines as analytical reagents¹⁻³, we have examined the reaction between rhodium(III) and methotrimeprazine (MTM) and proposed MTM as a new reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of rhodium(III). The method is elegant, sensitive, simple and offers unique advantage of the determination of rhodium in the presence of iridium.

Experimental

A stock solution of rhodium(III) was prepared by dissolving rhodium(III) chloride (0.8368 g) in 1 *M* hydrochloric acid (250 ml). It was standardised gravimetrically by precipitating rhodium as the sulphide, followed by ignition to the oxide and then reduction to the metal in presence of hydrogen⁴. A 0.2% aqueous solution of methotrimeprazine was prepared and stored in a refrigerator. Walpole buffers in the pH range 0.65-5.20 were prepared from 1 *M* sodium acetate (AnalaR) and 1 *M* hydrochloric acid (AnalaR) solutions. Aqueous solutions of 2% ascorbic acid and 0.05 *M* copper(II) sulphate were prepared from analytical grade reagents. Compounds of acceptable grades of purity were used in preparing other solutions used in interference studies.

Absorbance measurements were carried out on a Beckman DB spectrophotometer equipped with matched 1.0 cm glass cells, and pH measurements were made with a Elico L 1-120 digital pH meter.

Procedure : An aliquot of the solution containing up to 525 μg of rhodium(III) was transferred

† Presented at the 9th International Symposium on Microchemical Techniques, Amsterdam, August 28-September 2, 1983.

to a 25 ml volumetric flask. Sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid buffer (pH 2.5) (5 ml), 0.05 M copper(II) sulphate (1 ml) and 2% ascorbic acid (1 ml) and 0.2% MTM (4 ml) solutions were added to it. The solution was diluted to the mark with water, mixed well and allowed to stand for 50 min. The absorbance was measured at 495 nm against the reagent blank prepared identically without rhodium.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary investigations have shown that MTM reacts with rhodium(III) at room temperature in sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid buffer containing copper(II) sulphate and ascorbic acid as catalysts to form a red coloured rhodium(III)-MTM complex. Though, the colour development is initially rapid, 50 min time is required to attain the maximum absorbance. The absorbance values remain constant for 16 h. Heating the mixture containing rhodium with the reagents mentioned above on a boiling water-bath for various intervals does not improve

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra in NaAC-HCl buffer: (1) Rh³⁺, (2) reagent blank and (3) Rh³⁺-MTM complex. Rh = 10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, MTM = $7.3 \times 10^{-3} M$ and pH = 2.5.

the complex formation. At high temperature, the complex does not attain its maximum absorbance achieved at room temperature. It has been found that the complex undergoes dissociation on prolonged heating as shown by the decrease in absorbance as the rate of heating was increased. However, the absorbance readings remain constant in the temperature range 20-50° when the effect of temperature was

investigated in a thermostatic bath. Maximum intensity of the red colour of the complex is achieved over the pH range 1.5-3.5 in the presence of 0.8-1.5 ml of 0.5 M copper(II) sulphate and 2% ascorbic acid solutions. It is found that at least a 8-fold molar excess of the reagent is required to obtain maximum absorbance. The absorption spectra of reagent blank and rhodium(III)-MTM complex are shown in Fig. 1. The complex exhibits maximum absorption at 495 nm. The absorption spectra of the reagent blank show that it does not absorb around this wavelength. Beer's law is valid over the rhodium concentration range of 0.0 to 21 ppm. The sensitivity of the reaction as calculated from Beer's law data is 0.015 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and the molar absorptivity is $6.57 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The effect of foreign ions which often accompany rhodium was studied with 10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of rhodium. An error of $\pm 2\%$ in the absorbance reading was considered tolerable. The results show that no interference was noticed in the presence of Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Pb²⁺, U^{VI}O₆, fluoride, chloride, bromide, nitrate, sulphate, phosphate, acetate, oxalate, and EDTA. At least 2.0, 1.5 and 8.0-fold excess of Pt^{IV}, Os^{VIII} and Ir^{III} can be tolerated.

Composition and stability constant of complex: Job's method of continuous variation^{5,6} and mole-ratio method⁷ were employed to establish the composition of rhodium(III)-MTM complex. The determinations were made in a final volume of 25 ml and at pH 2.5 ± 0.1 . The results indicate the composition as 1:1. The observations at 465 and 525 nm also confirm the existence of only one complex. The apparent stability constant values of the complex were determined by two methods: the method of Foley and Anderson⁸ modified by Mukherjee and Dey⁹, and the mole-ratio method⁷. The log K values obtained for the complex at $27 \pm 1^\circ$ and pH 2.5 ± 0.1 are 4.2 ± 0.1 and 4.3 ± 0.1 , respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Bayer AG, Leverkusen, West Germany, for the supply of methotrimprazine. One of the authors (P. N.) acknowledges C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. B. KESHAVAN and P. NAGARAJA, *Analyst.*, 1981, 106, 464.
2. B. KESHAVAN and P. NAGARAJA, *Microchem. J.*, 1985, 31, 124.
3. B. KESHAVAN and P. NAGARAJA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, 22, 725.
4. F. E. BEAMISH, "The Analytical Chemistry of the Noble Metals", Pergamon, Oxford, 1966, p. 409.
5. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, 9, 113.
6. H. IRWING and T. B. PIERCE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 2565.
7. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.
8. R. T. FOLEY and R. C. ANDERSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1195.
9. A. K. MUKHERJI and A. K. DEY, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 18, 231.